

EXPLORING TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES ON THE UTILIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL VIDEOS: A CASE STUDY OF GENERATION X AND Y TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the perspectives of Generation X and Y teachers on the utilization of educational videos in classroom instruction, highlighting their roles in adapting technology to enhance teaching and learning. Guided by Sharan Merriam's qualitative case study framework, data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with six teachers—three teachers from Generation X born in 1967, 1970, 1973, and three from Generation Y born in 1992, 1994— at two schools in Dipolog City, Philippines. The findings revealed that both generational groups recognize the benefits of educational videos in enhancing student engagement, improving comprehension, supporting diverse learning needs, and managing classroom behavior. However, distinct generational differences emerged. Generation X teachers emphasized time efficiency, curriculum alignment, and source credibility, and Generation Y teachers highlighted interactivity, relatability, and personalized learning in educational videos. Challenges such as technological limitations, difficulties in video selection, and shifting student behaviors were reported across both groups. Additionally, teachers emphasized the importance of balancing video use with traditional methods and maintaining their role as facilitators of learning. The study concludes that educational videos are powerful tools, but their effectiveness depends on thoughtful integration, generational adaptability, and pedagogical balance. The recommendations provide practical guidance for teacher training, video content creation, and further research into generational teaching strategies in the digital era.

Keywords: *educational videos, Generation X teachers, Generation Y teachers, instructional technology, qualitative case study, teacher perspectives*

INTRODUCTION

As education advances into the digital age, technology plays an increasingly pivotal role in the classroom. Among the innovations that have enhanced the teaching and learning process are educational videos. Traditional teaching methods are evolving to incorporate videos as a powerful educational tool, which significantly improves student engagement and comprehension. These videos blend visual and auditory elements like animations, demonstrations, and real-life examples that help simplify complex topics and promote deeper understanding and retention of knowledge, making learning more interactive and memorable (Yap, 2020; Milnes, 2024). Research highlights videos' pedagogical benefits, including increased motivation, active participation, and deeper understanding through emotional design elements like visuals and sound effects (Sherin et al., 2009; Umayam, 2018; Uzun & Yildirim, 2023; Sharma, 2023). In addition, studies show videos foster curiosity, discussions, and self-paced learning, outperforming traditional instruction in engagement and outcomes (Martin & Bolliger, 2018; Almuslamani et al., 2020; Rongbuttsri et al., 2023).

Yet, teachers from Generation X and Generation Y approach these tools differently due to varying tech exposures. Related literature highlights generational differences in tech adoption among teachers. Generation X (born 1965–1980), dubbed "digital immigrants," often blend it cautiously with conventional approaches, adapting pragmatically but facing barriers such as tech skepticism and integration challenges since they adapt to digital environments later in life (Dimock, 2019; Çoklar et al., 2020). While, Generation Y (born 1981–1996), or "digital natives," grew up during the rise of the internet and digital technology, making them more comfortable with integrating technology into education, they are more receptive to it and seem to regard the use of technology as part of their teaching practice. The study by Li et al. (2015) explored how digital generation student teachers integrate technology into the classroom. The findings revealed that technology use was most strongly influenced by self-efficacy in teaching and computer skills. Moreover, despite being "digital natives," many student teachers expressed discomfort with the rapid pace of technological change and difficulties such as selecting developmentally appropriate content or aligning videos with curriculum goals.

The integration of technology in education is widely acknowledged for its potential to improve teaching and learning. However, there is still a limited understanding of how teachers, particularly across different generations, utilize contemporary tools and how such tools affect the teaching process, teachers' capacity to facilitate the delivery of lessons to meet the objectives.

This study aimed to explore the perception of Generation X and Y teachers regarding the practice of educational videos, and to explore the experiences, integration strategies, student responses, and challenges faced when using educational videos as tools for learning. The findings of this study contribute to a more complete understanding

of the effectiveness and limitations of video-based learning and offer practical recommendations to enhance strategies and engagement for educators and policymakers.

Research Questions

Central Question

- How do Generation X and Y teachers utilize educational videos in the teaching and learning process?

Sub-Questions

1. What are the roles of educational videos in teaching and learning as perceived by Generation X and Y teachers?
2. How do Generation X and Y teachers integrate educational videos into their instructional strategies?
3. How do Generation X and Y select educational videos for classroom use?
4. How do students respond to the use of educational videos according to Generation X and Y teachers?
5. What challenges do Generation X and Y teachers encounter in the utilization of educational videos?
6. What criteria do Generation X and Y teachers use to evaluate the effectiveness of educational videos in their teaching?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research approach to explore the perspectives of Generation X and Y teachers regarding their use of educational videos in the classroom. To guide the research process, the Merriam Case Study Model was adopted as the study's primary framework. Merriam's approach emphasizes understanding real-world educational experiences within a specific context.

This study was conducted in two schools in Dipolog City, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines: St. Vincent's College Incorporated – Basic Education Campus and Sta. Filomena Integrated School.

St. Vincent's College Incorporated– Basic Education Campus is a private Catholic school located on Padre Ramon Street in Estaka, Dipolog City, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines. It was selected for this research because it has a number of Generation Y teachers who were known to use educational videos as part of their teaching strategies.

Sta. Filomena Integrated School, a public school located in Sta. Filomena, Dipolog City, Zamboanga del Norte, was selected as the second investigation site because it is known for having many Generation X teachers. Their inclusion provides valuable insight into how Generation X utilizes educational videos in their teaching.

Six (6) teachers from Generation X (born 1967, 1970, 1973) and Generation Y (born 1992, 1994, 1995) participated, all actively using educational videos in formal classroom settings. To identify the participants, all participants were currently teaching in formal classroom settings and represented both Generation X (born 1965–1980) and Generation Y (born 1981–1996). As well, their inclusion was based on their use of educational videos as instructional tools, regardless of their level of mastery. The selected years were chosen to represent a diverse range of experiences within each generation.

Purposive sampling, a non-probability approach, was utilized to achieve the study's objectives. To ensure the sample was appropriately sized and relevant to the variables, participants were carefully selected based on their generational categories (Generation X and Y). This method ensured that the participants could provide valuable, relevant, and significant insights based on their own experiences, thereby ensuring that the data collected effectively addressed the research question.

The research instrument utilized for this study was a researcher-made semi-structured interview guide, featuring open-ended questions to explore teachers' experiences, attitudes, and insights on educational videos. No fixed number of items or Likert scale was applied; it prioritized qualitative depth for thematic patterns.

The interview guide was validated through advisor review, panel evaluations, revisions, and refinements to ensure comprehensive data collection and reliability.

Following Merriam's case study model, participants who use videos were purposively selected. The procedure began with the selection of participants, targeting Generation X teachers (born in 1967, 1970, and 1973) and Generation Y teachers (born in 1992, 1994, and 1995) based on the research objectives. Initial contact and consent were obtained through communication with each participant's respective academic institution, where the purpose, procedures, and ethical considerations were explained.

Semi-structured interviews were audio-recorded with participants' consent and transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy. After transcription, a member-checking process was conducted, allowing participants to review the recordings for accuracy.

For data analysis, thematic analysis was employed on the transcribed interviews to identify patterns, recurring themes, and insights related to video perceptions, strategies, student responses, and challenges. The findings were interpreted in conjunction with existing literature by comparing the collected data with prior research.

Finally, the researchers generated a comprehensive and accessible report detailing the research process, findings, analyses, and conclusions. This final step aimed to ensure that the results could inform future practices and reach a broad audience.

This research examines the perspectives of Generation X (1965–1980) and Generation Y (1981–1996) teachers regarding the integration of educational videos into their teaching practices. It explores their attitudes, strategies, and barriers related to

video-based instruction. The study includes six participants: three from Generation X, born in 1967, 1970, and 1973, and three from Generation Y, born in 1992, 1994, and 1995. These participants work at St. Vincent's College Incorporated – Basic Education Campus and Sta. Filomena Integrated School.

The research does not compare the two schools or include other generations, digital tools, or student learning outcomes. It should be noted that the study does not represent all teachers from Generations X and Y but specifically focuses on the selected individuals from the specified years. Due to the specific nature of the participants and schools involved, generalizations about all schools, regions, or educational systems in the country may not be easily made. While students' perspectives and learning processes are not within the scope of this work, the findings aim to provide valuable insights into how the generational groups examined utilize educational videos effectively in their teaching and learning processes.

RESULTS

1. Role of Educational Videos

Enhanced Comprehension and Engagement Through Visual Learning.
Across both generations, teachers highlight the power of educational videos in simplifying complex concepts and increasing student engagement. The visual and dynamic nature of videos is frequently cited as more effective than traditional, static teaching tools like charts and pictures.

"For me, it's more useful kay dali makasabot ang mga bata through videos." ["For me, it's more useful because children can easily understand through videos."] — (Gen X P1)

"Videos help by simplifying lessons step-by-step... Videos showing how clouds form are helpful because they have tangible images and motion that students can see." — (Gen X P3)

"Mas interactive siya jud kontra sa ikaw mo explain... mas okay man jud ng video, kay mura naman dayon syag direct example." ["It is really more interactive compared to when you explain it yourself... videos are really better because it's like a direct example right away."] — (Gen Y P4)

"With the use of video, dali rin nila makatch-up ang lesson." ["With the use of video, they can also easily catch up with the lesson."] — (Gen Y P5)

"Nag sige pud kog gamit especially sa robotics nga animated videos in order for me to catch the attention during my lessons." ["I also kept using especially animated videos in robotics in order to catch their attention during my lessons."] — (Gen Y P6)

This theme reveals that both Gen X and Y teachers recognize the strength of educational videos in making abstract ideas more concrete. Whether it is scientific processes or procedures, videos serve as a bridge between instruction and understanding, especially for visual learners.

Teaching Efficiency and Time Management for Teachers. Several participants from Gen X especially view videos as tools that reduce instructional burden and prep time, making teaching more efficient.

"Mas advantageous sa teacher kay less hassle and preparation." ["It is more advantageous for the teacher because there is less hassle and preparation."] — (Gen X P1)

"It saves us time... it really helps teachers since there are many videos available." — (Gen X P3)

"Okay, so what's the use? Madali ang dagan sa flow sa klase." ["Okay, so what's the use? The flow of the class runs more smoothly."] — (Gen Y P5)

The use of ready-made or easily accessible content on platforms like YouTube is seen as beneficial in managing workload, especially when explaining technical or content-heavy topics. Gen X teachers like Participant 1 and Participant 3 emphasized how videos streamline preparation and classroom delivery.

Addressing Diverse Learning Needs. There is a clear awareness that students have different learning styles. Videos are considered a flexible medium that can meet these diverse needs, particularly for visual and auditory learners and even slow learners.

"Labina sa mga maayo na bata attentive sila... sa mga bata na slow learner... Mas makakaton sila kay ilang man nakita o nadungog." ["Especially for the advanced students, they are attentive... for slow learners... they can absorb it more because they both see and hear it."] — (Gen X P2)

"Naay learning jud siya... naa tay gitawag na visual learners, naa man gitawag na about sound." ["There is really learning in it... we have what we call visual learners, and there are also those who learn through sound."] — (Gen Y P5)

Teachers are mindful of Howard Gardner's multiple intelligences or differentiated instruction principles. Videos allow learners to receive input visually and auditorily, and this inclusivity makes content accessible for a range of learners across comprehension levels.

Need for Instructional Balance and Reinforcement. While videos are praised, teachers from both generations stress that they should not fully replace traditional methods. Reinforcement, writing, and reading activities are still essential to deepen learning.

"They still need reinforcement... you need to help them absorb the concept." — (Gen X P3)

"Disadvantage kay magtinapulan na ug sulat ang mga bata. So it should be balanced... advise pod para sa inyong writing and reading comprehension." ["The disadvantage is that children will become lazy in writing. So it should be balanced... also advise them regarding their writing and reading comprehension."] — (Gen Y P5)

This theme underlines the critical pedagogical awareness that while videos are effective, they must be accompanied by active processing tasks. Gen Y P5 emphasizes maintaining a balance to ensure that learners still develop foundational literacy skills.

Behavioral and Motivational Impact. Teachers observed that videos have a behavioral effect, reducing classroom noise and increasing attentiveness, particularly for typically distracted students.

"Mapuyo gyud sila pay naay mga videos nga makita... lahi ra jud ang impact sa ilaa ang mga videos." ["They really settle down when there are videos to watch... the impact of videos on them is really different."] — (Gen Y P6)

"Attentive gyud sila... depende sa video if maayo ang pagka-deliver." ["They are really attentive... it depends on the video and how well it is delivered."] — (Gen X P2)

Video content appears to have a calming, focusing effect in classrooms, especially when the content is stimulating and well-produced. This is particularly valuable in managing classroom behavior, making videos both a cognitive and classroom management tool.

2. Integration of Educational Videos in Instructional Strategies

Strategic Placement of Educational Videos Across Lesson Phases. Both Generation X and Generation Y teachers consistently integrate videos at different stages of instruction, most commonly in motivation, discussion, and elaboration. This strategy enhances engagement and comprehension.

"I'm going to place it in my motivation. It could be from the start, pwede man. Even in your preparatory... In your review it depends on what apps you're going to use." ["I'm going to place it in my motivation. It could be from the start, that's fine. Even in your preparatory... In your review it depends on what apps you're going to use."] — (Gen X P1)

This reflects a flexible, strategic integration, aligning videos with specific parts of a lesson plan. Gen X Participant 3 highlighted similar adaptability:

"Kung naay process-oriented, para nindot akong lesson, magpakita ko ang videos sa motivation pa lang. Depende na lang kung kani ba siya na video ibutang nimo sa engagement, ibutang nimo sa elaboration." ["If it is process-oriented, for my lesson to be good, I will show videos as early as the motivation. It just depends on whether this video should be placed in engagement or in elaboration."] — (Gen X P3)

Generation Y Participant 5 echoed this:

"You can use videos for motivation and also for explanation when you get to the actual lesson, then you can use videos for the activity." — (Gen Y P5)

Generation Y Participant 6 described:

"Educational videos — I used them in motivation, and then after that proceeded to discussion and so on and so forth." — (Gen Y P6)

Teachers, regardless of generation, leverage videos to structure lessons around students' cognitive readiness, priming them through visual engagement, supporting elaboration, and reinforcing understanding. This indicates pedagogical awareness of learning phases and how videos can scaffold instruction.

Enhancing Understanding Through Visualization of Abstract or Complex Concepts. Videos serve as concrete aids for abstract or skill-based learning that is

otherwise difficult to demonstrate physically in the classroom. Generation X Participant 2 emphasized:

"So video plays as instructional support where there are times that you look for concrete support so they can both see and hear it." ["So video plays as instructional support — there are times when you need concrete support so students can both see and hear it."]

They gave a science lesson example:

"In science, that lesson on sources of light... You can see the examples of natural lights and artificial lights here." — (Gen X P2)

Generation X Participant 3 also illustrated this use in science:

"For example, the cycle to form clouds... they can really understand what comes first in the cycle... you can really assimilate the concept." — (Gen X P3)

Generation Y Participant 4 stressed the importance of visual demonstration in arts education:

"In contemporary arts, you really need to incorporate video so they can see how it is done... if you purely explain, they won't understand it." — (Gen Y P4)

Generation Y Participant 5 discussed practical constraints:

"We use video for first aid because not all materials are available to us. For example, bandage — how to apply it." — (Gen Y P5)

Generation Y Participant 6 made a strong case for deeper learning:

"Just looking for videos is easier for them to watch and they enjoy it more compared to just reading." ["Just looking for videos — it's easier for them to watch and they enjoy it more compared to just reading."]

"You can really see on their faces when I show a video... there is really something they learn from it." — (Gen Y P6)

Teachers recognize that some concepts, especially in science, arts, and skills training, require visualization to ensure understanding. This theme underscores how videos bridge the gap between abstract explanation and tangible learning, especially in resource-constrained contexts.

Leveraging Videos to Stimulate Engagement and Curiosity. Educational videos are used as engagement tools to hook learners' interest and sustain attention, often leading to deeper inquiry and enthusiasm.

Generation X Participant 1 exemplified this with a multisensory approach:

"In my own approach, I'm going to use pictures, videos... the mouth speaking in the video... or ears, with movement... you're also integrating another subject." — (Gen X P1)

The method not only engages but also encourages cross-disciplinary thinking.

Generation Y Participant 6 narrated a robotics lesson:

"I had them visualize... familiar cartoon characters... I compared them to robots existing in real life... I could see in the children that when I used that, they really had those 'aha' moments." — (Gen Y P6)

They emphasized the emotional and cognitive reaction:

"You can really see it on their faces... there is really something they learn and their attention span is longer." — (Gen Y P6)

The emotional and visual impact of videos activates curiosity and excitement. This is critical for Gen Z learners who thrive on media-rich content. Both generations of teachers consciously use video as a hook, showing their sensitivity to student engagement needs.

Purposeful Selection and Planning of Videos in Lesson Design. A recurring practice is intentional selection, teachers search and curate videos that precisely match the lesson objectives before actual instruction.

Generation X Participant 2 stated:

"Before you even make the lesson plan... you already look for a video that will coincide with your lesson... it's already in the video." — (Gen X P2)

This proactive approach ensures alignment with intended learning outcomes.

Generation Y Participant 4 noted:

"When you make your own lesson plan, in the motivation part, you need to relate it to your topic... you should provide a picture or video and decide which part to use and how to make it." — (Gen Y P4)

Generation Y Participant 5 reiterated:

"First, you can use videos for motivation... it should be balanced — we have ideas to present... we also have videos to show." — (Gen Y P5)

Both Gen X and Y teachers integrate videos by design, not by accident. They emphasize coherence between instructional goals and media content, illustrating strong planning habits rooted in pedagogical clarity.

3. Selection of Educational Videos

Alignment with Curriculum and Learning Objectives. Emergent across both Generation X and Y teachers, this theme underscores that the primary consideration when selecting educational videos is alignment with the curriculum, competencies, and lesson objectives.

"So, we have to check if it aligns with your MELCs or the Curriculum." ["So, we have to check whether it is aligned with your MELCs or the Curriculum."] — (Gen X P1)

"First, align it with your instructional goals." — (Gen X P2)

"Make sure it is just really aligned with what I want the children to understand in the lesson." ["Make sure it is really aligned with what I want the children to learn in the lesson."] — (Gen Y P6)

This theme emerges because both generational cohorts understand that any learning resource, including videos, must reinforce what is officially prescribed in the curriculum. The Matatag Curriculum and MELCs (Most Essential Learning Competencies) serve as benchmarks for instructional materials. Teachers emphasized that a misaligned video could lead to misconceptions, wasted time, or off-topic discussions.

Age-Appropriateness and Cognitive Level. Participants from both groups stress that educational videos should be appropriate for the age and comprehension level of the students.

"What if the video you showed is for high school, but your students are in elementary." ["What if the video you showed is intended for high school, but you are teaching elementary students."] — (Gen X P2)

"They are really interested... but you cannot use a video that is for Junior High School... it is too broad, already at college level, and they won't understand it." ["They are really interested... but you cannot use a video intended for Junior High School... it is too broad, already at a college level that Junior High students won't be able to understand."] — (Gen Y P4)

"Since I am teaching elementary, it also needs to be easy enough for my students to understand." — (Gen Y P6)

The theme shows that cognitive development is a major consideration. Participants are aware that mismatched complexity, either too advanced or too simplistic, negatively affects learning. Generation Y teachers particularly highlight tailoring the content complexity to student capacity.

Sensitivity to Culture and Gender. This theme, mostly discussed by Generation X teachers, reveals the value of inclusivity and sensitivity when showing videos in diverse classrooms.

"Gender-sensitive, so the student won't be bullied... The video should be gender-sensitive and not lead to bullying." ["It should be gender-sensitive, so no student gets bullied... The video should be gender-sensitive and must not lead to bullying."] — (Gen X P2)

"Choose a video that respects each culture. We are different — Cebuano, Muslim, Subanon." ["Choose a video that respects each culture. We are diverse — Cebuano, Muslim, Subanon."] — (Gen X P3)

Sensitivity arises from the multicultural and multi-gendered make-up of Filipino classrooms. Generation X teachers are more vocal about avoiding materials that may unintentionally marginalize students. This generational difference could be due to their longer exposure to institutional policies on diversity and inclusion.

Simplicity, Relatability, and Engagement. Participants across generations emphasize that videos must be engaging, simple, and relatable to ensure students' understanding and motivation.

"It should have simple representation, simple explanation... choose a video that is direct, purposeful, and relatable." — (Gen X P3)

"It should just be a simple video... so it can also connect to your class." ["It should just be a simple video... so it can connect to your class as well."] — (Gen X P4)

"Even if it is aligned, if it is not easy enough for the student... it should also be easy enough for my students to understand." ["Even if it is aligned, if it is not easy enough for the student to comprehend... it should be easy enough for my students to understand."] — (Gen X P6)

Engagement is not solely about entertainment but also about clarity and purpose. Simple and relevant videos help reduce cognitive overload, especially for younger learners. Generation Y teachers particularly noted the use of supplemental or segmented videos to maintain interest and increase clarity.

Visual and Auditory Clarity. Teachers look for videos that are visually and aurally accessible, particularly noting pacing, sound effects, and visual representations.

"Another thing — look for a video where the speaker does not talk too fast... otherwise the students will have difficulty keeping up." ["Another thing — look for a video where the speaker does not talk too fast... otherwise students will have a hard time keeping up."] — (Gen X P3)

"I presented a video about 'FANBOYS'... with matching sounds or effects, and a teacher who discusses it..." — (Gen X P1)

"For example, Rondalla Playing... and also health... we don't have a science lab." ["For example, for Rondalla Playing... and also for health lessons... we don't have a science lab."] — (Gen Y P5)

This theme emerges from practical classroom needs. Teachers, especially in resource-limited environments, depend on videos to substitute for labs or live performances. Clear visuals and slower narration help maintain comprehension among students with varying proficiency levels.

Pre-Screening and Content Validation. Teachers emphasize the importance of previewing videos to ensure accuracy, appropriateness, and safety.

"We really need to watch the video first — that is why we need to watch the videos beforehand." ["We really need to watch the video first — that is precisely why we must preview the videos."] — (Gen Y P5)

"You have to check the content of the video because other videos are not related or are already beyond the level..." — (Gen X P1)

Both generations underscore a shared professionalism: they do not randomly choose from online platforms like YouTube but apply discernment to validate each video's value and accuracy. Pre-screening avoids content errors, inappropriate materials, and irrelevant lessons.

Supplemental Role of Teacher. Teachers across both generations note that videos are not standalone; the teacher must still provide clarification and guided discussion.

"As a teacher, I will guide them more and provide extra information to make sure the students understand clearly." — (Gen X P3)

"At least you are there, and you can add on to help them." ["At least you are present, and you can add supplementary information to help them."] — (Gen Y P4)

Even with excellent videos, teachers see their roles as facilitators of learning. This theme reinforces that multimedia is a tool, not a teacher replacement.

4. Students' Response to Educational Videos

Increased Engagement and Participation. Both Generation X and Y teachers consistently observed that videos elevate student attentiveness, stimulate participation, and capture interest more effectively than traditional methods. Videos serve as visual and interactive stimuli that naturally draw learners in, especially in a generation accustomed to digital media.

"So, learners are more cooperative, attentive, and participative." — (Gen X P1)

"Since they can relate to the video, there's a higher chance of student participation and engagement." — (Gen X P2)

"Students are really engaged with videos." — (Gen X P3)

"They really enjoy it when there is a video — their focus is really captured and you get their attention." ["They really enjoy it whenever there is a video — their focus is really captured and you can get their attention."] — (Gen Y P6)

These statements underscore that videos significantly influence classroom dynamics by fostering active involvement, capturing attention, and allowing learners to engage more naturally and comfortably with the content.

Enhanced Comprehension and Understanding. Teachers emphasized that visual representation aids students in grasping abstract or complex concepts more easily. Through visualization, learners are able to make sense of ideas that would otherwise be difficult to understand through mere verbal explanation or text.

"Usually, when they understand, they really enjoy the video presentation. They would say 'Oh, so that's how it is, ma'am. I get it now, ma'am!'" — (Gen X P1)

"So the video really helped them understand the concepts better." — (Gen Y P4)

"That's how the process works — this is step 1, and that's the last step." — (Gen X P3)

"They got it more — they really understood the point I wanted to convey." ["They absorbed it better — they really grasped the point I wanted to convey."] — (Gen Y P6)

These remarks reveal how students often achieve the learning goals after viewing educational videos, gaining clarity and deeper comprehension that traditional teaching may not easily offer.

Personalized and Flexible Learning Experience. The ability to pause, replay, or select alternative videos based on personal preference adds a layer of learner autonomy. It enables students to adapt the material to their learning styles and revisit it as needed.

"Even if they don't fully understand it at first... if you give them the link, they can review and watch it again at home." — (Gen X P1)

"They can watch videos on YouTube and they can easily choose what video they prefer. So the child would say, 'This video is difficult, I'll look for another one.'"

["They can watch videos on YouTube and they can easily choose what video they prefer. So the child would say, 'This video is hard to understand, let me look for another one.'"] — (Gen X P3)

"It's just on their phone, they can watch it on YouTube." ["It's just on their phone, they can easily watch it on YouTube."] — (Gen Y P5)

This flexibility supports differentiated instruction and caters to varied comprehension speeds and learner needs, which is especially crucial in today's diverse classroom environments.

Emotional and Cognitive Stimulation. Educational videos provoke emotional reactions, excitement, fear, curiosity, which contribute to the cognitive process. The interplay between emotions and learning retention was evident in several participant comments.

"They have mixed emotions. Some are scared, while others are happy." — (Gen X P1)

"They were amazed because they saw that the video had motion. It entertained them." — (Gen X P2)

"Ahh, so that's what a cliff looks like, sir,' or 'That's the river, sir — now I get it.'" — (Gen Y P4)

These responses show how emotional engagement, when properly triggered through multimedia, contributes to better recall and understanding.

The Need for Varied and Contextualized Content. Teachers observed that student interest and understanding vary depending on the type and quality of the video. Not all students engage with the same material equally, and cultural or cognitive relevance matters.

"It depends on their focus. Some are out of focus because they don't know the reason. Truly, not everyone can understand it immediately." ["It depends on their focus. Some are out of focus because they don't understand the reason. Not all of them can grasp it right away."] — (Gen Y P5)

"Instead of using just 1 video, you should use 2 or 3, depending on where they can best adapt." ["Instead of using just 1 video, it would be better to use 2 or 3, depending on which one they can best adapt to."] — (Gen Y P5)

"As long as they can relate to it." ["As long as they can relate to the content."] — (Gen Y P6)

These observations highlight the necessity for teachers to consider multiple video options that cater to diverse learning styles and interests. Contextual relevance enhances relatability and comprehension.

Technology as Both a Tool and a Challenge. While videos offer significant educational value, the reliance on gadgets and digital familiarity also poses instructional challenges, especially for teachers adapting to tech-savvy students.

"They no longer like to read. So more likely, they won't see it." ["They no longer enjoy reading. So more likely, they tend to miss out on reading-based content."] — (Gen Y P4)

"The children know more than the teachers." ["The students are sometimes more knowledgeable than the teachers when it comes to technology."] — (Gen Y P5)

"We are not always perfectly versed — sometimes, especially because our audience is varied." ["We are not always perfectly versed in everything — sometimes this is especially true because our audience is diverse."] — (Gen Y P6)

These statements reflect a generational shift where students' advanced tech exposure demands that educators update and upskill themselves to remain effective facilitators of learning.

5. Challenges in the Utilization of Educational Videos

Technological Infrastructure Limitations (Power Interruptions and Internet Connectivity). Both Generation X and Y teachers cite technological limitations, particularly unstable power supply and poor internet connection, as primary obstacles

when integrating educational videos. These issues emerge due to the reliance of video-based instruction on electricity and digital networks, especially in areas where infrastructure is inconsistent.

"The number one challenge, of course, is when there's a power interruption because we can't show our video presentation..." — (Gen X P1)

"The internet connection is also a challenge..." — (Gen X P1)

"The connection is slow, and it's very difficult to keep adjusting the laptop." ["The connection is slow, and it becomes very difficult to keep on adjusting the laptop."] — (Gen X P2)

"The connection here is really very slow... it keeps loading." ["The connection here is really very slow... it just keeps on loading."] — (Gen X P3)

"Internet connectivity is also time-consuming when searching for a video." — (Gen Y P6)

"When I arrived at school, there was no connection at that time — that's just how it is." ["When I arrived at school, there was no internet connection at that hour — that's just the reality."] — (Gen Y P6)

These infrastructural problems make real-time streaming or spontaneous video presentations unreliable, pushing teachers to develop workarounds like downloading videos in advance. This is a recurring strategy for both generations, showing a shared adaptive behavior.

Difficulty in Selecting or Contextualizing Appropriate Videos. Another salient challenge is the effort required in selecting or contextualizing videos that match learning objectives, student comprehension levels, and cultural context. Teachers feel burdened by the abundance of content online but the lack of precision-fit materials for their classes.

"It takes a long time to look for a video that directly addresses your subject matter... since you have to first analyze what video aligns with your objective." ["It takes a long time to look for a video that directly addresses your subject matter... because you first have to analyze what video is aligned with your objective."] — (Gen X P2)

"Like, how do you relate — how do you find a video that is simplified and understandable." ["Like, how do you go about finding a video that is simplified and understandable for them."] — (Gen Y P4)

"Looking for relatable videos they can use in their practical lessons." ["Looking for relatable videos that they can actually apply to their practical lessons."] — (Gen Y P4)

"It is also time-consuming to search for a video because you need to find an appropriate video to give them." — (Gen Y P6)

This theme highlights the challenge of content alignment—not all readily available videos are usable. Generation Y teachers particularly stress the need for contextualization due to diverse student comprehension abilities. Meanwhile, Generation X teachers focus more on the front-end effort of video searching and preparation.

Generational and Technical Skill Gaps. Many Generation X teachers report difficulties in navigating technology, which is often attributed to the fact that they did not grow up with it. This gap affects their confidence and competence in using educational tech tools effectively.

"At my age, it is really very challenging when you have to keep adjusting the laptop." ["At my age, it is really very challenging when you have to keep on adjusting or troubleshooting the laptop."] — (Gen X P3)

"Technological skills — like with Kahoot, we don't really know how to use it well because we didn't have that before." ["Technological skills — like for instance with Kahoot, we don't really know how to use it well because we never had access to it before."] — (Gen X P2)

These struggles often result in reliance on tech-savvy colleagues or students. Teachers of Generation X are more likely to express challenges rooted in technological literacy, revealing a need for more robust support and training tailored to digital immigrants.

Shift in Student Behavior and Responsibility. Teachers from Generation Y observe that students today demonstrate a lack of responsibility and diminished attention span due to their interaction with technology. The shift from active note-taking to passive consumption (e.g., taking photos instead of writing) is seen as problematic.

"The challenge is that the children become out of focus." ["The challenge is that children tend to lose focus."] — (Gen Y P5)

"Instead of writing, they just take pictures. When they're done and their mom deletes the pictures, they'll say 'Our copy got deleted, sir.'" ["Instead of writing their notes, they just take pictures. But when their mom deletes the photos, they'll say, 'Our copy got deleted, sir.'"] — (Gen Y P5)

"Nowadays, we teachers are facilitators only... it's not like before." ["Nowadays, we teachers serve only as facilitators... it is no longer the same as it was before."] — (Gen Y P5)

This theme reveals deeper pedagogical implications, where technology, although meant to enhance learning, sometimes enables passivity and reduces student accountability. Teachers must adapt their strategies not just technologically, but behaviorally and motivationally.

Necessity for Backup Plans and Adaptability. Despite the challenges, both Generation X and Y teachers emphasize the need for adaptability, such as downloading videos in advance, switching to traditional teaching tools, or using personal mobile data.

"What I usually do is download the video and put it in my PowerPoint presentation." — (Gen X P1)

"As teachers, we also don't completely rely on educational videos... we use other materials instead, like the traditional ones — blocks." — (Gen X P3)

"To overcome it, you just need a backup data connection so you can still connect even without Wi-Fi." ["To overcome it, you just need to have a backup data connection so you can still connect to the internet even without Wi-Fi."] — (Gen Y P6)

This theme shows the resilience and innovation of teachers who creatively resolve problems when technology fails. It reinforces the idea that educational videos are tools— not replacements—for effective teaching.

6. Criteria in Evaluating the Effectiveness of Educational Videos

Student Engagement and Comprehension as Primary Indicators of Effectiveness. Both Generation X and Generation Y teachers heavily rely on how well students engage and comprehend content as a core basis for evaluating video effectiveness.

"After showing the video presentation, motivating questions follow — if they can answer the questions, it means they learned a lot from the video." — (Gen X P1)

This shows that Gen X teachers actively gauge students' responses through immediate questioning, using comprehension as a marker of effectiveness.

"If they were able to write, it means it is already effective... And then, to measure it is through assessment results. So if they get good scores... it means the video is effective." ["If they were able to write about it, it means it is already effective... And then, the way to measure it is through assessment results. So if they obtain good scores... it means the video is effective."] — (Gen X P2)

Here, the teacher uses written output and assessment results to determine effectiveness, connecting learning with observable performance.

"It is based on the students' engagement — so if the students really engage, participate, and apply skills from the video, then the educational video is effective." — (Gen Y P5)

The emphasis on active participation and skill application underscores how important behavioral and cognitive engagement are as criteria.

Assessment Performance and Score Outcomes as Objective Measures. Formal assessments serve as a vital tool in evaluating whether educational videos achieve learning goals.

"When I test them and they get high scores, that means the video is good and effective." ["When I give them a test and they score high, that confirms the video is good and effective."] — (Gen X P3)

The teacher directly links test performance to the video's instructional value.

"Okay, this is through testing only... there is already improvement because I used images and educational videos." ["Okay, this can be measured through testing... there is already improvement, because I used images and educational videos."] — (Gen Y P4)

The use of test-based evaluation and performance tracking across quarters shows how learning progression is attributed to video use.

"After the lesson, I assess the students — the results determine the effectiveness of educational videos." — (Gen Y P6)

For Gen Y teachers, regular assessment is a consistent mechanism to measure impact and adjust strategy.

Alignment with Learning Objectives. Teachers across generations also assess videos based on whether they align with intended learning objectives.

"I assess based on my objectives — if my objectives are met and the students' response is good." ["I assess it based on my objectives — if my objectives have been met and the response of the students is good."] — (Gen X P3)

This reveals that objective-based alignment is a precondition for considering a video successful. This criterion ensures that videos are not just engaging, but instructionally purposeful. It reflects a pedagogy rooted in alignment between goals, materials, and evaluation.

Source Credibility and Relevance. Some teachers, particularly from Generation X, emphasized the importance of the video source and its relevance to learning content.

"So when we talk about criteria — source. We have to check the source. If the source is reliable... then you check it against your rubrics." — (Gen X P2)

Teachers assess whether the material is credible and whether it fits within rubrics and lesson plans. This indicates a more structured, evaluative approach to content curation, suggesting that the authority and appropriateness of the source matter significantly in video selection.

Trial-and-Error and Reflective Practice. Particularly among Generation Y teachers, there is an emerging theme of using reflective practice and comparative effectiveness across classes.

"When I see that this video was effective in the first class... I use it in the next class... if it's not effective, I look for another one or I just don't use a video at all." ["When I see that this video was effective in the first class... I then use it in the next class... but if it turns out to be ineffective, I look for another one or I simply choose not to use a video at all."] — (Gen Y P6)

This illustrates a trial-based method of evaluating video content by testing it in one context before applying it in others. This iterative, reflective method reflects flexibility and adaptability in instructional practice, often characteristic of digital-native or transitional generations like Gen Y.

DISCUSSION

Role of Educational Videos

Enhanced Comprehension and Engagement through Visual Learning

Teachers across both generations recognized that educational videos make abstract and complex concepts easier to understand. The visual and dynamic content of videos helps in sustaining student attention and making lessons more interactive. Both Generation X and Y participants see videos as an effective way to capture students' attention and help learners stay focused and interested. Educational videos bring lessons to life by showing real-life examples, animations, and step-by-step processes that students can easily understand. This visual and interactive approach helps learners stay focused and interested, especially those who may struggle with traditional teaching method This finding aligns strongly on the study conducted by Angela Milnes (2024) on The Power of Video in Education: Enriching School Lessons highlights educational videos provide immersive visual and auditory elements that help bridge cognitive gaps they help simplify complex topics and promote deeper understanding and retention of knowledge, making learning more interactive and memorable.

Teaching Efficiency and Time Management

Teachers, particularly Generation X, integrate educational videos primarily to improve teaching efficiency and manage their time better. They find that using ready-made videos or accessible content reduces instructional burden and the need for lengthy preparation, especially when explaining content-heavy topics. These findings align with the study of Requillo and Bauyot (2024), which explored how Generation X teachers in Panabo City utilized educational technology. The study found that with the availability of online resources, teachers can quickly retrieve educational materials such as lesson plans, research articles, and multimedia content, reducing the time spent on manual preparation. This supports the idea that the use of educational videos is not only a strategic instructional choice but also reduces workloads among Generation X educators.

Addressing Diverse Learners' Needs

Both generations recognize that videos cater to diverse learning needs. Educational Videos are considered a flexible medium that can meet the diverse needs of the students, especially for visual, auditory, and slow learners, and even those who struggle to grasp lessons through traditional means since it allows learners to receive input visually and auditorily and this inclusivity makes content accessible for a range of learners across comprehension levels, this supports Sharma (2024) who noted video-based content caters to the diverse learning styles of students, particularly those who thrive in visual and auditory environments. By presenting information through videos, educators can effectively engage both learners, who absorb information through sight, and auditory learners, who learn best through listening. In line with Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences and differentiated instruction, where teachers tailor instruction in order to meet the diverse needs of the students.

Need for Instructional Balance and Reinforcements

While videos are praised for their effectiveness, teachers from both Generation X and Y observed that overreliance on them can lead to student passivity and a decline in essential literacy skills such as writing and reading. They emphasized the importance of balancing video use with traditional teaching strategies to ensure deeper learning. Generation X and Y stress that they should not fully replace traditional methods. Reinforcement is still essential to deep learning. Teachers highlighted the need to combine videos with follow-up activities like writing, reading, discussions, and hands-on tasks to reinforce concepts and enhance understanding. They agreed that videos should serve as instructional support, not replace the teacher's role in guiding learning.

This perspective aligns with Lev Vygotsky's Constructivist Learning Theory (1978), which emphasizes that learners build knowledge through active engagement and social interaction. While videos are useful for introducing content, meaningful learning is solidified through tasks that require learners to reflect, apply, and interact with the material.

Behavioral and Motivational Impact

Teachers noted that videos not only help with learning but also influence classroom behavior. Teachers observed that videos have a behavioral effect, reducing classroom noise and increasing attentiveness. Students tend to be more attentive, focused, and less disruptive during video-based lessons. Video content appears to have a focusing effect, especially when the content is stimulating and well-produced. This is particularly valuable in managing classroom behavior, making videos both a cognitive and a classroom management tool. This supports Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory; videos provide models of behavior that students can observe and imitate. When students see positive behaviors and academic engagement modeled in videos, they are more likely to reflect those behaviors themselves, which helps minimize classroom disruptions.

Integration of Educational Videos in Instructional Strategies

Strategic Placement of Educational Videos Across Phases

Both Generation X and Generation Y teachers purposefully integrate educational videos at various stages of instruction, most commonly during motivation, discussion, and elaboration. During the motivation, videos serve to introduce a topic in an engaging way to capture learners' interest and maintain their attention, often resulting in deeper inquiry and enthusiasm. This approach is supported by Sharma (2024), who emphasized that videos serve as powerful attention-getting tools that cater to visual and auditory learners, enhancing interest and emotional engagement.

In the discussion, videos are frequently used to break down complex concepts into manageable parts. Teachers may pause videos to emphasize key points or facilitate class discussions. According to Milnes (2024), videos help bridge cognitive gaps by providing visual representations that complement verbal explanations, especially useful for abstract or technical topics in science and math. During the elaboration, videos support deeper learning by helping students apply knowledge or analyze content from a new perspective.

Despite generational differences in digital fluency, both Gen X and Gen Y teachers share an awareness of how to match video content with learning objectives. Their use of videos shows a strong understanding of lesson structuring and scaffolding, ensuring that videos are not just supplementary materials but integral to the instructional flow. As noted by Martin & Bolliger (2018), this level of purposeful planning, such as aligning video content with curriculum goals and balancing the use of multimedia with other instructional method is essential for maximizing the educational impact of multimedia tools.

Enhancing Understanding Through Visualization of Abstract or Complex Concepts

Educational video serves as a concrete aid for abstract or skill-based learning that is otherwise difficult to demonstrate physically in the classroom. Both Generation X and Generation Y teachers recognize the limitations of verbal explanation alone, especially in subjects like science, arts, and technical skills, where it requires visualization to ensure understanding. Generation X teachers reported using videos to visually demonstrate lessons, allowing students to observe scientific concepts emerging in real time or through

animations. As noted by Milnes (2024), educational videos provide immersive visual and auditory elements that make abstract content more tangible and comprehensible, promoting deeper cognitive processing and long-term retention.

Similarly, in skills-based or performance subjects—such as first aid training, robotics, or contemporary arts—videos are used to model techniques and procedures. Teachers explain that access to all physical equipment isn't always possible; therefore, video recording becomes very important for demonstrating concepts and real-world applications. This aligns with Sharma's (2024) observation that videos support diverse learning styles by offering a visual representation of ideas, benefiting learners who struggle with textual or auditory instruction alone.

Leveraging Videos to Stimulate Engagement and Curiosity

Educational videos serve as an effective tool to capture students' interest and nurture their attention, often leading to deeper exploration and enthusiasm. The emotional and visual impact of videos stimulates curiosity and excitement, which is essential for students who thrive on media-rich content. Teachers notice that students are visibly more engaged and attentive when videos are integrated into lessons. For example, when lessons include animations, music, or relatable characters, students respond with curiosity and enthusiasm, frequently asking follow-up questions or demonstrating deeper reflection. These "aha" moments, as noted by teachers, illustrate how videos can ignite inquiry and enhance a student's eagerness to learn more. Both generations of teachers actively utilize video as a hook, demonstrating their awareness of student engagement needs.

Research supports this observation, the study of Almuslamani et al. (2020) on the effect of educational videos on increasing student classroom participation: Action research. The study highlights that educational videos have a direct and positive impact on increasing student participation in the classroom. When videos are incorporated into lessons, students become more actively engaged by asking questions, sharing opinions, and discussing topics, which promotes curiosity. Additionally, passive participation—such as listening attentively and taking notes—also improves, making this an effective strategy for enhancing student engagement.

Purposeful Selection and Planning of Videos in Lesson Design

Teachers from both generational cohorts point out the value of pre-selecting videos that align with lesson objectives. Teachers from both Generation X and Generation Y emphasize the importance of pre-selecting videos that align with lesson objectives. This practice ensures coherence and promotes instructional clarity. Both Gen X and Y teachers integrate videos by design, not by accident, highlighting the connection between their instructional goals and the media content. Their strategic use of videos aligns with Sorden's (2013) study on the cognitive theory of multimedia skill development, which suggests that effective instructional strategy design should follow principles such as clarity, pacing, and contextuality to maximize student learning outcomes. Moreover, structured lesson planning that incorporates videos in a thoughtful manner encourages a

purpose-driven teaching approach, where instructional decisions—including the use of videos—are firmly grounded in curriculum standards and pedagogical objectives.

Selection of Educational Videos

Alignment with Curriculum and Learning Objectives

The primary consideration when using educational videos in the classroom is ensuring they align with the curriculum, competencies, and lesson objectives. Both Generation X and Y teachers recognize that the effectiveness of video integration relies on this alignment. Any skill development resource, including videos, must support what is explicitly outlined in the curriculum. To achieve this, they intentionally select videos in advance to ensure that the content directly addresses specific learning objectives. They prioritize credible sources that provide accurate, informative, and clear explanations, especially for abstract or complex topics that are challenging to demonstrate in class.

Teachers are guided by frameworks like MELCs and the MATATAG Curriculum, emphasizing that video content must support instructional goals. This echoes findings by Martin & Bolliger (2018), who argue that instructional videos should align with curriculum goals to promote meaningful skill development. This observation supports the idea that the use of video in the classroom is not accidental; rather, it is a strategic choice rooted in formal educational standards.

Age-Appropriateness and Cognitive Level

Teachers from both generations emphasize the importance of selecting videos that are suitable for the age and comprehension level of the students. Their concern arises from the cognitive dissonance that occurs when the complexity of a subject does not match the level of understanding of the students. Participants recognize that imbalances in the level of detail—whether the material is overly complex or too simplistic—can hinder the learning process.

Generation Y teachers particularly highlight tailoring the content's complicated nature to student capacity. This corresponds with the rationale of the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, mainly the segmentation and modality principles. Likewise, teachers should select short, focused videos with clear spoken narration rather than lengthy, text-heavy content. This approach acknowledges that cognitive overload can hinder learning. By intentionally choosing and designing videos that avoid unneeded information, teachers can give content in manageable chunks to ultimately maximize student understanding.

Sensitivity to Culture and Gender

Primarily, emphasized by Generation X teachers, this theme shows a conscious effort to respect cultural diversity and gender sensitivity in the classroom. Their cautious approach may reflect longer exposure to policy-driven inclusivity training, namely those informed by the Gender and Development (GAD) framework among the Filipino people.

The GAD mandates the integration of gender sensitivity and responsiveness in all aspects of education, along with instructional materials.

This supports the claim by Chan & Lee (2023), who also mention that generational differences affect sensitivity levels toward classroom diversity and inclusion, with Generation X teachers tend to exhibit more caution and thoughtful consideration, often questioning whether the media they use respects cultural norms and avoids reinforcing stereotypes or exclusion.

Simplicity, Relatability, and Engagement

Teachers stress that videos should be easy to understand, direct, and relatable to ensure students' understanding. Engagement is not solely about entertainment but also about clarity and purpose. Simple and relevant videos help reduce cognitive overload, particularly for young learners. This practice aligns with the Limited Capacity Assumption in CTML, which posits that learners can only process a finite amount of information at once. Videos that are overloaded with complex narration, excessive text, or irrelevant details can overwhelm students. Gen Y teachers can particularly note the use of supplemental videos to direct their teaching toward student accessibility and the teacher-student relationship. Focus more on how students emotionally and visually connect with video content. They often choose videos that are familiar and exciting—such as animations or real-life scenarios—reflecting their sensitivity to student interests and their goal of increasing engagement and motivation through relatability.

Sari et al. (2023) report similar observations as Çoklar et al. (2020) about Gen X teachers being cautious, practical users of digital tools, while Gen Y teachers use digital tools with ease in a flexible manner, maintaining their focus on educational standards.

Visual and Auditory Clarity

This theme stems from practical concerns—especially in resource-limited classrooms where videos often substitute for labs or live performances. The teachers require videos with clear audio, slow narration, and strong visuals. Clear visuals and slower narration help maintain understanding among undergraduates with varying skill levels. Again, Sharma (2024) confirms that videos catering to both visual and auditory learning styles are more effective. Since videos provide visual representation of ideas and a wealth of visual cues, including images, graphs, animations, and diagrams, to enhance understanding and retention.

Pre-Screening and Content Validation

Teachers across both generations affirm the need for previewing and evaluating video content before classroom use. Pre-screening avoids content errors, inappropriate materials, and irrelevant lessons, certifying that students are exposed only to precise and meaningful content. Their caution exposes professional thoroughness and a need to avoid misinformation or inappropriate content, mainly from channels like YouTube.

Supplemental Role of the Teacher

Teachers across both generations acknowledged that educational videos are not replacements for teachers, but instead tools that support instruction. While videos can present content visually and audibly, teachers remain indispensable in facilitating discussions, clarifying concepts, and guiding students through application and reflection.

This perspective strongly supports Lev Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory of Learning, especially the concept of the More Knowledgeable Other (MKO). A learner can do independently what they can achieve with guidance from someone who greater extent skilled—typically, a teacher. In this framework, the teacher serves as the MKO, providing scaffolding—the temporary support that helps students progress through learning tasks until they can perform independently.

Videos, while rich in content, are static and impersonal; they cannot interact with students in real time, adjust explanations based on misunderstanding, or tailor feedback to individual needs. Teachers, on the other hand, can observe cues, ask questions, and mediate learning experiences, ensuring that students are not only absorbing content but also engaging with it meaningfully. The teacher remains central to the learning process, using multimedia to enhance, not replace, their instructional strategies.

Students' Response to Educational Videos

Increased Engagement and Participation

Both Generation X and Y teachers consistently observed an increase in student engagement when educational videos were used in the classroom. Learners appeared more cooperative, attentive, and participative compared to traditional instruction. Videos serve as visual and interactive stimuli that naturally draw learners in because videos use bright visuals, movement, sound, and sometimes fun animations or real-life examples. These features make learning feel more like watching something enjoyable rather than doing something boring, especially in a generation accustomed to digital media.

This reflects findings from the study of Almuslamani et al., (2024), on the Effect of Educational Videos on Increasing Student Classroom Participation: Action Research, supports that educational videos are inherently visual and dynamic, making them more engaging than traditional text-based or lecture-style learning. The combination of animations, music, and familiar characters stimulates curiosity and excitement, which is particularly effective for Gen Z learners who thrive on media-rich content. When students are captivated by a video, they are more likely to stay focused and actively participate in discussions. Providing immersive audiovisual stimuli that foster active participation can help.

Enhanced Comprehension and Understanding

Both generations emphasized that visual representation aids students in grasping abstract or complex concepts more easily. Through visual representation, learners are capable of making sense of ideas that would otherwise be difficult to understand through

mere verbal explanation of the text. Teachers emphasized that pupils "finally get the point" after watching a video, making connections that verbal explanations fail to achieve. Educational videos help simplify complex matters through visual modeling, making lessons more tangible and relatable. On top of that, step-by-step video explanations improve pupils' ability to accomplish multi-stage tasks, especially in subjects like science and mathematics. The participants reported that video integration results in better test results and also improves classroom attendance patterns.

This finding agrees with Bandura's Social Learning Theory, which posits that people acquire new knowledge and behaviors by observing others. When students watch instructional videos, they are exposed to modeled demonstrations, narratives, and explanations, allowing them to understand complex ideas through observation rather than abstract verbal instruction alone.

Personalized and Flexible Learning Experience

Teachers noted that the ability to pause, rewind, and rewatch educational video recordings allows the students to engage with the material based on their personal learning preferences. This aids pupils who battle to keep up during live instruction, as they can revisit the content at their own pace. Educational videos support self-paced learning, which is essential for meeting the different needs of the students. This flexibility promotes differentiated instruction by accommodating varied comprehension speeds and learning styles, leading to improved understanding and retention. This supports the claim by Rongbut Sri et al., (2023) that different educational video formats enhance learning experiences by allowing individually timed learning, which supports differentiated instruction. This flexibility caters to different comprehension speeds and skill development styles, ultimately leading to improved understanding and retention among students when undergraduates were allowed to select their own educational videos; their classroom participation increased more compared to videos chosen by the teacher.

Emotional and Cognitive Stimulation

Another powerful theme was the emotional response evoked by videos. Teachers saw how pupils respond with excitement, fear, and curiosity, which contribute to the cognitive process that captures their attention as well as enhances memory and understanding.

Emotional engagement, when properly triggered through multimedia, leads to better recall and understanding, making skill development experiences more memorable. Video's ability to present real-life scenarios, animations, and storytelling creates emotional hooks that deepen the learning experience. This is particularly useful in teaching abstract or unfamiliar topics. Uzun and Yildirim (2023), students' experiences with emotional design in multimedia learning, highlighting how emotional elements like color, facial expressions, and sound effects enhance engagement and understanding, enhancing learning by increasing interest and ultimately contributing to better recall and making learning experiences more memorable.

The Need for Varied and Contextualized Content

Cultural relevance of digital learning materials emphasizes the integration of cultural contexts to enhance educational engagement. For instance, digital storytelling featuring myths and legends not only made learning engaging but also instilled a sense of pride in students' cultural identities. In the same way, Generation Y Teachers observed that student interest and understanding vary depending on the type and quality of videos. Not all students engage with the same material equally, and cultural or cognitive relevance matters. Videos that are too technical, outdated, or unrelated to the students' culture or background might lead to confusion or disinterest. This highlights the necessity for teachers to consider multiple video options that meet the diverse needs of students. Ensuring that the materials are suitable for their age, knowledge level, and social context enhances relatability and comprehension.

Technology as Both a Tool and a Challenge

According to Almacen and Labitad (2024), multimedia-enhanced learning can transform traditional teaching methods by fostering greater student engagement and academic improvement. By incorporating visuals, audio, and interactive elements, multimedia tools help students grasp complex concepts more effectively, making lessons more immersive and memorable. The positive shift in students' attitudes suggests that technology not only improves comprehension but also enhances motivation, as learners feel more connected to the material. Despite the benefits, educators often face challenges in keeping pace with rapidly evolving technology. Lisenbee (2016), the generation gap between students and teachers in classrooms regarding technology use. The lack of digital fluency among teachers limits classroom innovation. This disconnect affects student engagement and effective technology integration in education. teacher training programs that support effective technology integration, ensuring that students can fully utilize digital tools for learning

Challenges in the Utilization of Educational Videos

Technological Infrastructure Limitations (Power Interruptions and Internet Connectivity)

One of the most recurrent and pressing issues raised by both Generation X and Y teachers is the technological limitations, particularly unstable power supply and poor internet connections, as primary obstacles when integrating educational videos. These issues emerge due to the reliance of video-based instruction on electricity and digital networks. In areas with inconsistent infrastructure, reliance on educational videos becomes problematic. These infrastructural problems make real-time streaming or spontaneous video presentations unreliable, pushing teachers to develop workarounds like downloading videos in advance. Despite their generational differences, both cohorts adapt by preloading materials, suggesting a shared coping mechanism. Arayata (2023), although videos can enhance instruction, their impact diminishes when teachers face basic access issues. Further supporting this theme, a study by Ilesanmi and Etsename (2022), on 'Teacher perceptions of the use of videos for teaching and learning, claimed

that significant challenges are due to limited access to necessary equipment and technical skills. The lack of resources such as projectors, computers, and reliable internet connectivity hindered the effective integration of videos into teaching.

Difficulty in Selecting or Contextualizing Appropriate Videos

Another salient challenge faced by both Generation X and Y teachers is finding the right educational videos that truly match what they are teaching. It's not enough to just pick any video online—teachers must make sure it fits the lesson's goal, is understandable for their students, and matches the students' background or culture. This means that even though the internet offers *a lot* of videos, most of them are not exactly what teachers need. This theme highlights the challenge of content alignment—not all readily available videos are usable. Generation Y instructors feel the need to adjust videos for different types of pupils, as Generation X teachers commonly struggle with the time and effort of video searching and preparation. According to Bitzenbauer et al. (2024), teachers habitually rely on surface features such as thumbnails, likes, and views rather than content-related aspects when preferring videos. This reliance can lead to the selection of videos that may not align well with curriculum objectives or student needs, underlining the struggle of finding appropriate and contextually relevant video materials. On top of that, educational videos hold significant promise for enhancing teaching and learning; their effective utilization is often impeded by challenges in selecting and contextualizing appropriate content.

Generational and Technological Skill Gaps

Many Generation X reported a noticeable struggle with operating digital tools and platforms, which is often attributed to the fact that they did not grow up with them. This gap affects their confidence in using educational tech tools effectively. These experiences match what Çoklar et. al. (2020) said: Individuals in this generation witnessed the emergence of digital technologies but did not grow up immersed in them. As a result, they tend to be skeptical about technology and find it harder to utilize since they adapt to digital environments later in life. Further, Generation X teachers who began using technology relatively into their teacher training are more likely to be pragmatic rather than impulsive in their use, attributing technology to pedagogy. Another study by Sari et. al. (2023) generation X teachers use videos for instructional support, communication, and collaboration, yet digital problems persist due to varying levels of ability, access, and experiences to adapt video integration in teaching.

Shift in Student Behavior

Technology doesn't just change how teachers teach—it also affects how students behave and learn. Many Generation Y teachers have noticed some worrying changes in their students ever since digital tools like smartphones and videos became common in the classroom. The shift from active note-taking to passive consumption (e.g., taking photos instead of writing) is seen as problematic. Instead of actively participating in class—like writing notes, thinking deeply, or joining discussions—some students now just watch videos or snap pictures without really processing the information. This kind of

behavior shows a shift from active learning, where students are engaged and thinking, to passive learning, where they just absorb content without much effort. This theme reveals deeper pedagogical implications, where technology, although meant to enhance learning, sometimes enables passivity and reduces students' accountability. This concern is supported by Heflin et al. (2017) that while students perceived mobile technology positively in learning, it also contributed to disengagement during class. Speech and eye contact were identified as strong indicators of engagement, whereas distractions from mobile devices led to reduced participation. Notably, students who composed responses on mobile devices demonstrated significantly less critical thinking compared to those using handwriting.

Necessity for Backup Plans and Adaptability

Even though teachers from both Generation X and Y face problems, both generations demonstrate a commendable level of resilience and adaptability, such as downloading videos ahead, switching to traditional teaching, or using personal mobile data. Some teachers download videos ahead of time and insert them into their PowerPoint slides. This way, even if the internet is slow or there's no connection, they can still show the videos to their students. Others switch to traditional tools—like using blocks, charts, or printed materials—when videos are not an option. This theme shows the resilience and innovation of teachers who creatively resolve problems when technology fails. It reinforces the idea that educational videos are tools- not replacements for effective teaching. A study by Zara et al. (2022) during the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted how teachers adapted their teaching strategies. Educators demonstrated flexibility by redesigning lesson plans, utilizing blended learning approaches, and creating contextualized modules to meet students' needs. This clearly illustrates the important role of teachers in being adaptable and navigating various challenges while still addressing the demands of their students.

Criteria in Evaluating the Effectiveness of Educational Videos

Student Engagement and Comprehension as Primary Indicators for Effectiveness

Both Generation X and Generation Y instructors emphasize student engagement and comprehension as fundamental factors in evaluating the effectiveness of educational videos. Teachers observe how students interact during or after watching videos—for example, responding to questions, participating in discussions, or producing written outputs—to assess their levels of understanding and involvement. The emphasis on active participation and skill application underscores the importance of behavioral and cognitive engagement as criteria. As outlined by Tseng (2021), the effectiveness of educational videos was examined, and it was found that teacher annotations play a crucial role. By timely prompting students for questions and reflections, teachers significantly enhance learning. The investigation highlights that students benefit more from watching educational videos when guided by teacher annotations, rather than watching them passively. Students reported that their retention and comprehension of the video content improved with the support of these annotations.

Assessment Performance and Score as Objective Measures

The study conducted by Noel Calo on the Effectiveness of the Contextualized Audio-Video Materials on the Test Scores of the Grade 5 Pupils in Mathematics: Basis for Instructional Supervision (2024). The study findings highlighted significant improvement in students' test scores after integrating the materials into instruction. The learners grasp mathematical concepts, as evidenced by the marked increase in their assessment scores. Like Generation X and Y teachers, formal assessments serve as an imperative device in evaluating whether educational videos achieve skill advancement goals. Teachers often rely on numeric evidence, such as test scores and written assessments, to determine video effectiveness. Both Generation X and Generation Y teachers note that the use of video can improve performance, and they consider high scores as indicators of the effectiveness of television in enhancing learning. For Generation Y teachers, ongoing assessment is a vital method to evaluate impact and adjust their teaching strategies accordingly.

Alignment with Learning Objectives

Meng (2023) aligns instructional practices with education quality standards is essential for ensuring that students receive the highest quality education and achieve optimal learning outcomes. Effective instructional practices have a direct impact on student engagement, motivation, and achievement. When instructional practices are aligned with established quality standards, they create a consistent and rigorous learning experience for all students. This alignment ensures that instructional methods, materials, and assessments are designed to meet the specific needs of learners and promote their academic growth.

Teachers across generations frequently evaluate educational videos based on their alignment with desired learning outcomes. A recurring theme emphasizes that video content directly supports the instructional objectives outlined in the curriculum. Regardless of how engaging a video might be, it must effectively address the specific competencies or goals set for the lesson. When students demonstrate through their responses or behavior that they have met these achievement objectives, teachers consider the video to be effective. This criterion emphasizes that educational videos must not only capture students' attention but also serve a clear instructional purpose. This approach promotes coherence among educational goals, instructional materials, and assessment methods.

Source Credibility and Relevance

Teachers, particularly from Generation X, emphasize the value of video sources and their relevance in understanding content. For Generation X educators, assessing the credibility and relevance of video sources is an essential step in the selection process. This reflects a more structured and evaluative approach to curating content, where the reliability of the source plays a significant role in choosing videos. They often rely on rubrics or established standards to determine if a video is suitable for classroom use. This indicates a more cautious and practical method for integrating curated content. This aligns

with the findings of Çoklar et al. (2020) and Sari et al. (2023), who noted that Gen X teachers, though digitally adaptive, are more skeptical and pragmatic in using technology. They often examined sources to ensure that instructional materials are reliable, relevant, and appropriate

Trial-and-Error and Reflective Practice

A unique theme among Gen Y teachers is the use of trial-and-error and reflective practices to determine a video's effectiveness. A trial-based method of evaluating with different videos across classes and reflecting on student reactions and outcomes. If a video proves ineffective in one setting, they either adapt or replace it. This reflective method reflects flexibility and adaptability in instructional practice, often characteristics of digital-native generation like Gen Y. This theme resonates with Chan & Lee (2023) Gen Y teachers, grew up during the rise of the internet and digital technology, they are more receptive to it and seem to regard the use of technology as part of their teaching practice making them comfortable with integrating technology in education are comfortable with exploring, modifying, and integrating digital tools.

Conclusions

Educational video application in classroom settings received investigation from Generation X and Y teachers as part of this research initiative. Rather than viewing educational videos as a mere supplementary tool, both generational cohorts recognized their potential in boosting student interest while handling subject material better and raising learning outcomes. What distinguishes the two groups, however, is not their acceptance of educational videos but the motivations and methods guiding their use. Teachers use specific evaluation guidelines that include a selection of videos that match educational goals while being easy to understand and culturally sensitive, and that provide appropriate pacing alongside clear communication. Generation X teachers focused on maintaining curriculum and educational standard compliance, yet Generation Y teachers set their priorities on making content connectable and approachable for learners. This generational contrast enriches our understanding of how teaching philosophies shape video integration.

The research revealed several challenges that teachers from different generations experience. Representatives from both Generation X and Generation Y faced distinct issues related to technology. However, they did not view these challenges as major obstacles. Both generations emphasized the importance of the teacher's role in guiding learning, ensuring that videos enhance rather than replace meaningful instruction. Grounded in Mayer's Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning and Mannheim's Generational Cohort Theory, this research affirms that educational videos are more than technological aids (Mayer, 2021; Mannheim, 1952). They are dynamic tools to foster students' interest and engagement, shaped by the generational experiences, digital fluency, and pedagogical beliefs. These findings deepen our understanding of how technology, pedagogy, and learner engagement intersect across generations.

Recommendations

Recommendations from the study research involve the following:

Teachers. Teachers from Generation X need specific training on technical aspects of video implementation as part of their professional development. Generation Y teachers should participate in instructional workshops that focus on teaching students how to discipline themselves while using videos.

School Administrators. School administrators should implement three support measures, including dependable Internet service as well as backup power equipment combined with ongoing information technology skill development, to achieve smooth video-based teaching.

Educational Content Creators. The responsibility of Educational Content Creators is to create videos that suit diverse cultural insights and match local classroom learning requirements through straightforward materials written for students at the correct developmental stage. Subtitles, together with language options, help students when they face comprehension problems.

Researchers. Future research should address the study limitations by evaluating Generation Z teachers in addition to their student participants and a larger educational demographic. Student opinions must also be included, as they would provide vital insights into educational video effects on the classroom environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Some ethical concerns were observed in order to respect participants' rights. Firstly, participants' consent is collected, making the participants understand the rationale for the research, the processes to be followed, and the possible risks involved in the research.

In this case, confidentiality is another ethical issue that was also embraced. The participant profile was maintained by giving assurance to the participants and by guaranteeing the confidentiality of the information collected. In the analysis of data collected for the study, no data were portrayed with direct recognition of the teachers or their respective institutions.

Thirdly, respondents' privacy was also considered in the data collection. Participants were able to decide what aspects of the information about them they want to reveal. These research workers followed such guidelines as not asking leading questions and using data collected solely for research. The study also considered the ethical principles laid down by the institution conducting the study, as well as other ethical committees.

Finally, the transparency of the study was maintained throughout. A set of descriptions of aims and objectives of the study, sources of data collection, and data

analysis procedures was completed in advance to give participants understandable and concise information. Subsequently, participants were offered the right to review the results if it was of their concern. This helps to guarantee that the research process adheres to the high levels of ethical standards.

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